

Examining the Nexus between Service Delivery Efficiency and Sustainable Operation of Coffee washing stations in Gashonga sector, Rusizi District

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ABSTRACT

This study is entitled “The impact of service delivery on firm sustainability in Gashonga sector, Rusizi district”, it aimed to determine the influence of service delivery on firm sustainability. The study intended to assess the level of service delivery and firm sustainability and investigate the challenges and mitigation strategies for service delivery by coffee farmers toward firm sustainability.

The study employed 330 as target population. Stratified sampling was used to get sample size, 18 manpower workers, 58 coffee farmers.

The findings of the study revealed that service beneficiaries perceive the importance of good service delivery. it was proved that service delivery has a positive impact on business sustainability. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .112$) revealed that 11.2% , and Provision of branches can improve service provided by our firm. My firm organize field work to visit their stakeholder in their firms correlate with Business has enough tools to reach everywhere ranked on ($R = .361$, $P = .001$) the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .130$) revealed that 13.0%. My firm provide enough training to their works ($R = .537$, $P = .000$), The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .288$) ranked by 28.8%. The firm receive our complaining immediately and verbally as the way of improving customer care, The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .244$) ranked by 24.4% ($R = .491$, $P = .000$). The service delivery is attractive in our region ($R = .313$, $P = .006$), The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .097$) ranked by 9.7%. The firm give us different kind of motivation as to keep relationship with their customer and attract new ones ($R = .251$, $P = .029$), The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .063$) ranked by 6.3%.

Key words: Washing station, service delivery

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable services are privileged worldwide, as for as service delivery and business sustainability are concerned in Europe, Hananel, C. (2019) state that “many studies show that companies that commit to sustainability are financially to outperforming their competitors. Offering sustainable product and services could be next steps for large and small firms or business. Today only 33% of all SMEs within European union offer sustainable products or services while the market demands in all sectors” he also confirms that “environment awareness has been rising steadily in Europe, both within companies and among citizens. According to a Poll, 94% of Europeans think that the protection of the environment is important. Citizens and companies are well aware of environment threats, particularly plastic waste, climate change, energy use, water use, material waste and other threats to biodiversity.” Hananel, C (2019) add that following workshop offered by public bodies, public or private labels in most European union countries, small business can extend their offer with environmentally friendly products and services, while large firm can build a new market with resources efficient, eco designed products.

As for as service delivery and sustainability are concerned in the USA, Toyota T.(2017) state that in 2015, research has proven that people were preferring even to pay more for sustainable services and goods” the survey found that nearly three out of four respondent were willing to pay between 10% and 25% more for sustainable products and services.” Most sustainable service delivering companies have more growth than those which are not sustainable. This highlighted as follow. “These companies enjoy remarkable share price growth of 29% in 2017 to 22% for the ones offering unsustainable services and goods.” He adds that “society in the USA is demanding that companies, both private and public serve a social purpose. To prosper overtime, every company must not only deliver financial performance but also show how it make a positive contribution to society. Companies must benefit all their stakeholders, employees, customers and the community in which they operate.

Concerning the continent of Africa as far as the issue of service delivery associated with sustainability is concerned, Craig, D. (2019) find that same imperatives have not been developed : “while some African countries and companies are among the fastest growing in the world, their attitudes toward environment, social and governance imperatives have not developed at quite the same pace.” It is added that business model and structure have yet to implement sustainable values to ensure the security of global investment partners’ input as well as the empowerment of generation to come. Briefly it is highlighted that companies in Africa still have a long way to go so as to deliver sustainable services. Craig, D. (2019) explains it as “publically available data on African companies still have a long way to go in order to manage resources in sustainable way, develop management model that recognise the value of all members of the workforce and develop way of doing business that keeps African accountable to their principle as well as to their communities.”

In East Africa, county like Kenya measures have been taken to direct services delivery toward sustainability. Mwangi, P.(2016) shows that the government of Kenya has started creating an environment in which business can align their service with sustainability activities with nationally identified priorities and has actively engaged in setting framework for implementation through policy standard and legislation. The government will also continue to empower local business operation while offering them new near complete autonomy in creating locally relevant approach, initiatives and operations. They will also speed effort in assisting development organisations and regional companies in adopting professional approach to their impact, aligning their strategies toward sustainable development, setting commitments and targets and measuring and reporting on performance. Therefore, the government has proposed a structure that will assist new and existing companies in developing business that are economically viable in the long run.

In Rwanda, service delivery has been mandated to RGB (Rwanda Governance Board). According to RGB, improved service delivery is not only expected to increase profitability and attract investment to boost the county’s economy, but also it is a strong principle to ensure that citizens’ rights to different services respected. Concerning sustainability, Mbabazi, D. (2020) asserts that environmental consciousness and sustainability have become priority among the general population of resources in bid to enhance a balanced environment. Service delivery which does not respect sustainability can affect different people association with the business. Concerning business owners, sustainability implies that business profit. Drucker, P. (2018) said that “a successful business is the one that makes an acceptable profit now and in future.” In addition to that, Deming, W.E. added that small firm or business success require delighting

customers. Thus, same business fails as a result of not delivering a delightful service to their customers. Beaver, G. (2003) state that having poor communication skills with employees and customer appear to be a marker for failure. Cochran, A.B. (198) state that small business failure is often measured by the cessation of a firm's operations.

Concerning customers and the community in general, business owners should deliver their service aiming at a profit without forgetting the welfare of people and the environment. Sustainability does not only imply profit but also people and environment. It is in this framework that business owners should be encouraged to deliver sustainable services. It means that they need to bear in their mind that while delivering their service, they should maintain healthy environmental, social and economic systems in balance both on a global and local scale. Pacas, J. (2019).

Therefore, it is clear that delivering unsustainable service and products can have negative effect in different ways. Business men can lose their customers which can then result in their business failure. This can also be damaging to the health of customers, workers, the community and the environment. As an example, Draper, M. (2019), argues that business today may adopt technology without a long-term integration strategy then this could eventually affect sustainable profits and employee retention. Like poor environmental processes which create excessive waste and depend on resources that cannot be replenished, bad business practices waste potential revenue and burn out a company's resources.

Improvement of service delivery towards sustainability is much needed. When service delivery is linked with sustainability, there is more chance for business improvement. Pacas, J. (2019) showed that the value of sustainability to business service is cost savings, increasing talent, and reputation and retention of customers. Concerning cost saving, business leaders need to care about their resource efficiency, waste management, water reduction and energy conservation. To increase or attract talented workers, business need to link sustainable services to social integrity and target. As for reputation and retention of customers, Pacas, J. (2019) confirms that accountability and transparency rise in importance. He states that customers who want more than affordability are increasingly seeking products and services that positively impact the society and the environment.

It is understandable that people run businesses in order to make profit. The source of that benefit is the business customers. In contrast, a business may fail as a result from different factors among others poor service delivery to customers. Therefore, the root of the conception of this research is to study the role of service delivery in the sustainability of SMEs. According to Investopedia, sustainability consists in meeting the needs of the present without

compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs. Therefore, sustainability is beneficial to different parties among others: business owners, employees, customers, the community and the environment.

1.2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Service delivery can impact on the success or failure of an enterprise. Importantly, excellent service delivery may also influence business sustainability. Sustainability implies equitable consideration of profit, people and environment while running a business. On the other hand, poor and mediocre service delivery may cause the failure of a business. This is due to the fact that there can be some problematic cases where some businesses are started and after a comparatively short time their activities stop and their service is lost. Other enterprises are able to prosper and grow from a lower category to a higher one; whereas they accumulate their profit without taking into consideration the welfare of people and the environment. Additionally, people or customers, specifically, may be denied some clients rights or may be delivered a service which is not fair i.e. which does not respect the principles of sustainability. Boulder, C. (2015).

1.3. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This research aims at investigating the contribution of service delivery in boosting the sustainability of enterprises. It is in this framework that it is guided by general and specific objectives.

1.4. Research objectives

Specifically, this study is intended to accomplish the following objectives:

1. To establish the level of service delivered to coffee farmers
2. To examine the contribution of service delivery on coffee firm sustainability
3. To find out the challenges faced by coffee farmers in terms of service delivered by the coffee firm
4. To propose strategies to enhance service delivery towards firm sustainability.

1.5. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research is to be carried out to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of service delivered to coffee farmers?
2. What is the contribution of service delivery on the sustainability of coffee firm?
3. What are the challenges faced by coffee farmers regarding service delivered by coffee firm?

4. What are strategies to enhance service delivery towards firm sustainability?

1.6. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The fulfilment of this study is useful to different people which are grouped into 3 categories of interest:1.6.2. Social Interest

Entrepreneurs will benefit from this study because they will be provided with a good literature to help them run their business sustainably. The society as a whole will benefit from this research because they will be delivered good service as a result. Additionally, customers' knowledge and perception about service delivery will be increased by the fulfilment of this study.

1.6.3. Scientific Interest

Researchers in some domains related to entrepreneurship, economics, business studies, etc. will benefit from this research as it can be a source of reference as far as other academic researchers are concerned.

1.8. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of this study is to be delimited as geographical, content, and time scope.

Geographically, this research is delimited in Rusizi district, Gashonga sector. As we can't cover all firms in the district. The researchers have chosen Gashonga Coffee Factory which is a coffee washing station based in Rusayo cell, Gashonga sector, Rusizi district.

Concerning the content, service delivery and business sustainability involve a lot of factors which cannot be covered in one study. It is in this framework that we have set the objectives to investigate the impact of service delivery on business sustainability focusing on the people to be delivered the service i.e. customers' appreciation and perception.

The time scope is three years ranging from 2019 up to 2022.

2.2. THEORITICAL RIVIEW

2.2.1. Factors of Service Delivery

Johnston, R. and Graham, C. (2008) highlight that the delivery of a service typically requires six factors:

Service provider (workers and managers), Equipment used to provide the service (e.g. vehicles, cash registers, technical systems, computer systems, etc), Physical facilities (e.g. buildings, parking, waiting rooms, etc), Service consumer, Other customers at the service delivery location, Customer contact. It is added that service delivery requires the service encounter

which is defined as all activities involved in the service delivery process. Some service managers use the term "moment of truth" to indicate that point in a service encounter where interactions are most intense. Johnston, R.& Graham, C. (2008).

2.2.2. level of service delivery by coffee farmers

Coffee farmers told us what they think about a brand or a company or its offerings. It can be positive or negative feelings, perceptions, inhibitions, predispositions, expectations or experiences that a customer has. (Bhasin, H. 2017). Perceptions of a service are a complex series of judgments formed during or at the end of the experience. (Williams and Buswell, 2003).

2.2.2.1. Customer Service Quality Measurement

Parasuraman, Zeithalm and Berry (1985) developed the customer service gap model which is a gap method in service quality measurement aiming at both identifying the gaps between customer expectations and the actual services provided at different stages of service delivery and closing the gap and improve the customer service. This model identifies five different gaps in delivering quality service:

The customer gap is the gap between customer expectations and customer perceptions level the customer gap is the difference between customer expectations and customer perceptions. Customer expectation is what the customer expects according to available resources and is influenced by cultural background, family lifestyle, personality, demographics, advertising, experience with similar products, information, etc. Customer perception is totally subjective and is based on the customer's interaction with the product or service. Perception is derived from the customer's satisfaction of the specific product or service and the quality of service delivery. In an ideal world, the customer's expectation would be almost identical to the customer's perception. Therefore, in a customer oriented strategy, delivering a quality service for a specific product should be based on a clear understanding of the target market. Understanding customer needs and knowing the customer expectations could be the best way to close the gap.

The knowledge gap is the gap between consumer expectation and management perception the knowledge gap is the difference between the customer's expectations of the service provided and the company's provision of the service. In this case, managers are not aware or have not interpreted the customer's expectations in relation to the company's services or products.

To close the gap between the consumer's expectations for service and management perception of service delivery will require comprehensive market research.

2.2.3. Barriers to Customer Service Delivery

Lebed, M. (2015) discusses barriers to effective service delivery which enterprises' service team should avoid. Below are 10 most common and most significant mistakes which are to be prevented so that customers may have a truly outstanding customer service.

Indifference: the way a customer service agent is approaching a client, his/her attitude toward the client is extremely important. It may seem that some technical aspects of how support is being offered have bigger impact. However, in my experience, the quality of a personal interaction between the agent and the customer always has bigger contribution to how customer evaluates his experience. She says: "In my opinion, indifference lies at the root of all other barriers to a great customer experience. It is what nurtures slacking and creates a negative impression in customers, that's why I put it as the first and the most significant barrier..." (Lebed, M., 2015). Inattention the natural consequence of indifference i.e. inattention to the voice of the customer also creates a negative impact and make the customers feel as if their business is unimportant to you. Customers want to be heard. Not only they expect you to understand their problem and offer a solution, but they also want you to hear their feedback, their complaints, compliments and suggestions. They want you to notice what they say, react to it and respond.

Lack of commitment: A lot of the times a customer's issue requires a follow up. There may be some cases that a customer service agent and a company as a whole do not have the necessary commitment to lead the customer to the end and ensure that his problem is solved and the customer is satisfied. According to Bell, D., et all (2002), also Poor team work it may happen that the customer was served perfectly well during the first interaction, but when his issue is escalated to another person, or he gets in touch with another team member during a second interaction, he experiences disappointment. The need to explain the issue a second or third time, or sometimes different answers, different interpretations of the company policy given by agents can greatly diminish customer experience. Make sure that your team is strong and gives consistent experience to the customer. All members of the team should work in cooperation, every link of the chain supporting the next one.

Overworking: a few customers declare that whenever they contact support, a lot of the times their problem is interpreted to be larger than it is. Overworking the problem can be as damaging as underworking it. Good knowledge of the product or service, attention to the customer's explanation of the issue and some degree of intuitiveness will help the agent to see the real scope of the problem and give the fastest and the simplest solution (Kathol, R. G., Butler, 2010).

Scripted communication: Customers desire authenticity and dislike overly scripted service. Many companies, unfortunately, deviate into scripted communication with their clients. Partly, it happens because it is easier for companies like this. It also happens because companies don't trust the discretion of their employees that they can sort out the client's problem. So they give them canned responses to send to customers.

According to Lebed, M. (2015), Lack of customer personal data or insufficient use of it: Customers find it important that the company has access to their previous transaction history and their personal details. Not collecting any customer information, as well as collecting but not making use of it is equally damaging to how customers perceive your support. Make sure that you are asking your customers only that information which is needed and you are using it to the maximum to provide better service to them.

Delayed response: Nobody likes waiting. Long hold times are one of the most frequent causes of complaint and dissatisfaction by customers. This seems like the easiest thing to fix. However, many companies still overlook this important aspect of good service as fast reaction to a customer service request.

2.2.4. Key Elements of Service Delivery System

There are four key elements of service delivery system which are the following according to Ankerstjerne, P. (2019):

Service Culture: It is built on elements of leadership principles, norms, work habits, vision, mission and values. Culture is the set of overriding principles according to which management controls, maintains and develops the social process that manifests itself as delivery of service and gives value to customers. Once a superior service delivery system and a realistic service

concept have been established, there is no other component as fundamental to the long-term success of a service organization as its culture.

Engagement: According to Ankerstjerne, P. (2019), Employee Engagement includes employee attitude activities, purpose driven leadership and Human Resources processes. Even the best designed processes and systems will only be effective if carried out by people with higher engagement (Wilkinson, L., & Grimsrud, A. 2020). Engagement is the moderator between the design and the execution of the service excellence model

Service Quality; It includes strategies, processes and performance management systems. The strategy and process design is fundamental to the design of the overall service management model. Helping the client fulfil their mission and supporting them in the pursuit of their organizational purpose, must be the foundation of any service provider partnership Seyitoğlu, F., & Ivanov, S. (2020).

Customer Experience: It includes elements of customer intelligence, account management and continuous improvements. Perception is king and constantly evaluating how both customer and end-user perceive service delivery is important for continuous collaboration. Successful service delivery works on the basis that the customer is a part of the creation and delivery of the service and then designs processes built on that philosophy – this is called co-creation.

2.2.5. Service Delivery Strategies

P. Weinzimer (2014) tackling the issue of service delivery strategies discussed seven steps to excellent service delivery as they were highlighted by O’Conner.

Identify business and commodity services required by business units this consists in meeting the leaders of the Marketing, Sales, Finance, and other key business units to understand the business, the competitive marketplace, and the specific services each business unit needs to achieve their objectives (P. Weinzimer, 2014). Identify key stakeholders and priority for each business service the objective for this step "is to validate the list of business services, the key stakeholders, and level of service required." This is like fostering business partners and employees’ availability.

Develop enterprise list of business services this is about developing a consolidated list of all the business services required for each business unit including the priority of the services as well as the understanding of the value of the business service provided. Crane, M. F et all (2022)

Socialize across Enterprise Socialising implies some objectives among others: communicating so as to understand the business services required to support the major processes of the company; and sharing the level of service required by the business to meet their goals. Continuously Improve Every successful executive knows that implementing a continuous improvement program is a smart thing to do. This is an excellent method for improving performance. Michael, O. N., Peterson, M. O., (2022), show that to evaluate regularly the level of service. This provided all the key stakeholders, IT service owners, business owners, and business users the opportunity to be part of a service delivery improvement program."

Develop / Execute Work Plan service delivery team such as IT and business unit personnel gather in order to review the data collected during the previous few months and develop a realistic work plan. P. Weinzimer (2014) Measure Service Delivery this consists in measuring the performance of each service at the root level. This philosophy is simple. It intends to get at the root problem for every service disruption. "If you solve the root problem, the disruptions will not reoccur."

Continuously improve every successful executive knows that implementing a continuous improvement program is a smart thing to do. This is an excellent method for improving performance. Michael, O. N., Peterson, M. O., (2022), show that to evaluate regularly the level of service. This provided all the key stakeholders, IT service owners, business owners, and business users the opportunity to be part of a service delivery improvement program."

2.3.1. Characteristics of Sustainable Business

Matthew Tueth (2017) suggests that a mature and authentic sustainable business contains six essential characteristics:

Triple top-line value production(TTL): "The TTL Establishes three simultaneous requirements of sustainable business activities: financial benefits for the company, natural world betterment, and social advantages for employees and members of the local community with each of these three components recognized as equal in status." Many businesses use the triple bottom line (TBL). Matthew Tueth (2017) show that Nature-based knowledge and technology. This biomimicry-based principle involves the conscious emulation of natural-world genius in terms of growing our food, harnessing our energy, constructing things, conducting business, healing ourselves, processing information and designing our communities."

Products of service to products of consumption Products of service are durable goods routinely leased by the customer that are made of technical materials and are returned to the manufacturer and re-processed into a new generation of products when they are worn out. (These products are mostly non-toxic to human and environmental health but toxic materials that are used will be kept within a closed loop type system and not be able to escape into the environment).

Products of consumption are shorter lived items made only of biodegradable materials. They are broken down by the detritus organisms after the products lose their usefulness. (These are also non-hazardous to human or environmental health). This principal requires that we manufacture only these two types of products and necessitates the gradual but continual reductions of products of service and their replacement with products of consumption as technological advancements allow.

Solar, wind, geothermal and ocean energy. "This principle advocates employing only sustainable energy technology solar, wind, ocean and geothermal that can meet our energy needs indefinitely without negative effects for life on earth." Other authors, such as Paul Hawken (2022), have referred to this as utilizing current solar income. Continuous improvement process Operational processes inside successful organizations include provisions for constant advancements and upgrade as the company does its business. The continuous process of monitoring, analyzing, redesigning and implementing is used to intensify TTL value production as conditions change and new opportunities emerge.

2.3.2. CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES OF SUSTAINABLE SERVICE

Miranda, C. (2019) who is a researcher and a sustainable business consultant has made a research about running a small business sustainably. She declares that she is herself a small business owner and attest that running a small business is challenging enough without adding one more thing to it; hence, sustainability brings its own set of challenges such as not having the money to make the changes that you want, not having enough time to do it all, not having employees who are engaged with your sustainability efforts.

Following the survey that Miranda, C. (2019) has carried out among business professionals and small business owners, she has come up with the most common challenges to small businesses sustainability, along with strategies for overcoming those obstacles.

The strategy here is to begin with projects that have a good payback. Also look for rebates and assistance to help you with your projects, since many organizations and utilities are available to help small businesses. For example, almost all projects related to energy efficient lighting will have a good payback since they result in an immediate decrease in your energy bill and there are many rebates available. This helps to both free up some money *and* demonstrate the business case for sustainability initiatives, which can help to secure additional funding for future projects. Miranda, C. (2019), Challenges related to time of changes there are actually three strategies that you can use here. First, focus on your top priorities. You won't be able to do everything at once, so you'll need to clearly establish your priorities and focus on those first; everything else will have to wait. Identify initiatives that are aligned with your overall business goals, have a significant impact, and have a good payback and prioritize those. Second, build a team. Having a green team will enable you to receive input from other employees and get help with your initiatives so that you're not doing it all yourself. Lastly, look for ways to integrate sustainability into what people are already doing. Sustainability shouldn't be a standalone project that is relegated to one department or one person. Ideally, it should be *a* way of thinking and doing that considers the social and environmental impact of all that you do. For example, HR is already working on onboarding new employees – how can sustainability be integrated into that? Marketing is already working on communications – how can telling your sustainability story be a part of that?

to have employees who are engaged, you need to give them opportunities for engagement. This might seem obvious, but you would be surprised at how many times I talk to business owners who wish that employees were more engaged, but yet haven't created channels for them to get engaged. In his book *Drive: The Surprising Truth about What Motivates Us*, Dan Pink identified three elements that create true motivation in people – autonomy, mastery, and purpose. If you want employees to be engaged, you need to allow them to have some autonomy, some say in the initiatives that your business is working on, and that must contribute to their sense of purpose. This is also in line with what the experts recommend for engaging employees in sustainability. One of the best ways to do this is to form a green team.

Miranda, C. (2019), also implies that Lack of knowledge about business sustainability. here, the strategy used by many businesses and the one that is recommended is to use existing frameworks such as Green Business Certification. If you're just getting started, you can build on the proven best practices that other businesses have used. Time and again, I hear business professionals say that they learned a lot by going through the process of getting these certifications. Especially in

combination, these two certifications will provide frameworks that you can use to ensure that you're building a good sustainability foundation for your business. An added benefit is that you'll also get some public recognition for your efforts.

This is quite understandable. You're busy, you don't have enough time, and sustainability is a quickly evolving field. Unless you work in this field (and even if you do), it can be a challenge to stay on top of all of the changes. To complicate things further, when it comes to small business sustainability, there is no one place that you can go to get the latest information. You need to stay up-to-date with online developments, you'll also get regular access to someone who can help you—you don't have to do this alone. Rana, M., & Parves, M. (2011), Culture challenge this usually becomes evident when only a minority of individuals at a company is thinking about sustainability. You can take a three-pronged approach to addressing this. First, getting buy-in from management is key because it will allow rank-and-file employees to feel that they have support from above. Second, you'll need to expand sustainability beyond just one department so that it is a company-wide endeavor. This will also help with employee engagement. Lastly, education is key. Providing sustainability training to employees can make a significant difference. Culture change is slow, but educating and engaging employees will move you in the right direction.

Reporting can range from producing a formal annual sustainability report using. If you're just getting started, you'll need to do some work to identify the areas that you'll focus on and then set some targets for those areas. For example, if you would like to be more energy efficient, you might set a goal to reduce your energy usage by 10%. Once you've set some targets, you can share that information internally with employees (who of course should be allowed to provide input on those targets) and you can decide how much to share externally. Some businesses choose to share their targets publicly, while others might just share updates about changes that they have been making. In either case, you'll want to be authentic, (Dey, P. K., 2020)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. RESEARCH APPROACHES AND DESIGN

This research consists both qualitative and quantitative research approaches. Qualitative approach is to be used while describing and interpreting data. There are some questions that need to be investigated and some objectives which are to be achieved during the process of this

research. Then qualitative research approach is used to discuss the findings. In addition, quantitative research approach is to be used to analyze the data into numbers and frequencies.

Concerning the design, this study uses descriptive survey which involves asking questions in form of questionnaire to different groups of individuals. This design is suitable for this research because it is used in the framework to find answers to research questions.

3.2. TARGET POPULATION

The target population is the population that the researcher used to generalize the findings of the study (Muganda, 2003). In this study, researchers base their study on coffee firm in Rusizi district. We chose one enterprise which is known as Gashonga Coffee Factory, a coffee washing and drying station which is located in Rusayo cell, Gashonga sector. The target population consists of 330. The target population was divided into two major categories which were the factory working staff and coffee farmers. The factory working staff consisted 80 people, the coffee farmers were 250 people.

Table 1: table of targeted population distribution

Participant categories	Number	Percentage
Working staff	80	24.24%
Coffee formers	250	75.76%
Total	330	100%

Source: Primary data, July 2022

3.3. SAMPLING PROCEDURES

Sampling is a method that allows researchers to infer information about a population based on results from a subset of the information, without having to investigate every individual. Barratt, H. (2009). In this research, probability (random) sampling technique has been chosen because in this way a researcher starts with a complete sampling frame of all eligible individuals from which the sample is selected; and then all eligible individuals have a chance of being chosen for sample.

There are different types of random sampling. Here we used random sampling because all population were able to provide information needed by the researcher. Stratified sampling

method was applied. Barratt, H. (2009) highlights that in this method, the population was first divided into subgroups (or strata) who all share a similar characteristic. In this research, the stratified sampling consisted of two groups of people which make a large group of the target population of 330 people. The first group was composed of the concerned enterprise working staff (80 people), the second group was made of the coffee farmers neighboring to the coffee washing station (that is 250 farmers belonging to the station's zoning area) The formula which was used to calculate the sample was based on Solvin's (1960) formula which is $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$. The formula is well explained in the sample size subchapter.

3.4. SAMPLE SIZE

Since all target population cannot be contacted, researchers must find a smaller manageable number of respondents or sample size which was selected from the target population. As stratified sampling method has been chosen for this research, stratified random sample is to be calculated. To arrive at the sample size of this research, the researchers advocated proportionate stratification approach. Solvin's formula asserts that "with proportionate stratification, the sample size of each stratum is proportionate to the population size of the stratum. Strata sample sizes are determined by the following equation: " $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$."

$$n = \frac{330}{1 + 330(0.1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{330}{1 + 330(0.01)}$$

$$n = 330/4.3$$

$$n = 76 \text{ population}$$

Muganda (2003) proposes that the total sample size should be at least 10% of the total population when the population sampled from is relatively large, and 30% for a relatively smaller population depending on time resources available for the research. In this research the total sample size taken is 10%. Therefore, taking into consideration the number of people in each group of the target population, (the factory working staff i.e. 80 people, farmers i.e. 250 people), the formula is applied as follows:

The sample size for the group of the factory workers is $(80/330) * 76 = 18$.

The sample size of the group of farmers is $(250/330) * 76 = 58$

Therefore, the total sample size is 76 people.

Table 2: table of sample size from the population

Participant categories	Number of sample size	Percentage
Working staff	18	23.6%
Coffee farmers	58	76.3%
Total	76	99.9%

Source: Primary data, July 2022

3.5. DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

There are two categories of data to be collected in this research i.e. literature from different authors and information from research respondents. For literature review, we proceeded with books and online documentation. Concerning the information from respondents, the researchers preferred the use of questionnaire as a research instrument and interview guide. They introduce themselves and present the letter requesting for the permission to obtain information to the administrative staff. After being welcomed in the mentioned enterprise, they presented the questionnaires to their respective respondents and guide them to fill in the questionnaires appropriately.

3.7. DATA ANALYSIS

The data were analyzed using SPSS, where data were presented in mean and standard deviation and also frequency table and in equivalent percentage on interview data. Data analysis consists of different steps such as editing, coding, classification. After collecting the data, editing will follow through which the data is to be reviewed to check for its completeness and consistency, detect errors so as to correct them. Since data is collected, coding will be needed so as to refine and organize it before analyzing it. Short phrases are to be used as the codes to describe different categories of collected information. Then, in the evaluation of the data, the researchers will assign percentages to the given codes in order to draw inferences. Concerning classification, it was used to group data under various homogenous groups. In this respect, the data in this research will come from 4 different classes: the business office staff, manpower workers, coffee farmers and coffee sellers. Then, classified data was arranged in tables in order

to calculate percentages. Tabulation and frequency percentages was for drawing frequency distribution tables.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Level of service delivery by coffee farmers

Service is being done to serve and satisfy both service providers on gathering live hood and on other hand service consumers who came as user of service, therefore the data obtained on perception of service delivery by service beneficiaries or to customer of the business where customer express their attitude to word the service they get from Gashonga coffee. The level of service delivered to coffee farmer is indicated by mean where mean range is 1 to2.0 is lower, 2.0 to2.50 is low, 2.50 to 3.0 is high, 3.0 to 3.50 is higher.

Table 5: Level of service delivered to coffee farmer

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
The business satisfy (meet with) our expectation	76	2.27	1.18
My firm engage in delivering process	76	2.13	.914
The firm infrastructure favour the customer to work with firm	76	2.91	.278
My firm engage me in service delivery and to play may port in different activities	76	2.00	1.166
I always use the service of this business	76	2.55	.900

My business collaborate with us through communicating and visiting us on flied	76	2.57	1.226
I access easily the financial document of the firm as the way to ensure our working security	76	1.99	1.216
Different platforms of the firm help us to share every information and experience	76	2.09	1.073
Valid N (listwise)	76		

Source: Primary data, July 2022

The table five shows the mean values for scores of perceptions of service delivery on service beneficiaries. The respondents showed that the business satisfy (meet with) our expectation were low (Mean=2.27, SD= 1.18). My firm engage in delivering process were low (Mean=2.13, SD= .914). The firm infrastructure favour the customer to work with firm ranked high (Mean=2.91, SD= .278). My firm engage me in service delivery and to play my port in different activities were ranked low (Mean=2.00, SD= 1.166). I always use the service of this business were high (Mean=2.55, SD= .900). My business collaborates with us through communicating and visiting us on flied ranked (Mean=2.57, SD= 1.226). I access easily the financial document of the firm as the way to ensure our working security were low (Mean=1.99, SD= .1.216). Different platforms of the firm help us to share every information and experience was low (Mean=2.09, SD= 1.073). those data implies that most of respondent show that there is low mean this show that firm still have many thing to work as the way to improve their levels of service delivery to their customers.

4.2 Contribution of services delivery on firm sustainability

The firm or business sustain depend on the contribution to what service business is providing to the society that encourage customer to work with them this make the researcher to find out what Gashonga coffee contribute to their customer.

Table 6: Contribution of service delivery

Model	Beta	P value (sig)	Partial
The facilities at my firm help me to increase my welfare	.521	.000	.521
The seminars planed by firm help us to get open mind and become more creative and innovative in our operation	.519	.000	.529
To get firm in our local area has increase infrastructure in our region	.226	.003	.250
The firm arrangement improve social welfare	-.282	.002	-.351
The firm contribute to social activities to improve standard of living like umuganda and other programs	-.230	.002	-.269
Corporation of firm and local formers help us to get different training and link us with other formers	.285	.001	.386
Our firm increase employment opportunity in our local area	.388	.000	.453
The exploitation of our product make my work to be productive	.278	.005	.324

Source: Primary data, July 2022

Table 7, indicates the results of The facilities at my firm help me to increase my welfare $\beta=.521$, p value =.000; The seminars planed by firm help us to get open mind and become more creative and innovative in our operation $\beta=.519$, p value .000; To get firm in our local area has increase infrastructure in our region $\beta=.226$, p value .000; The firm arrangement improve social welfare $\beta=-.282$, p value =.002; The firm contribute to social activities to improve standard of living like umuganda and other programs $\beta=-.230$, p value 002; Corporation of firm and local formers help us to get different training and link us with other formers $\beta=-.285$, p value .001; Our firm increase employment opportunity in our local area $\beta=.388$, p value .000; The exploitation of our product make my work to be productive $\beta=278$, p value =.005; this indicate that the mean 6.33 and standard deviation .973, the point that we get from this respondent show that there is there is relationship between those items that improves the quality of life to mean that business contribution to world society is

important and their contribution play a lot to their client according to what respondents say they need more to contribute as to improve their working condition in their daily life.

4.3 Strategies to enhance service delivery to word firm sustainability

The firm to sustain require to set proper and strong strategies that guide their work and improve their performance level of implementation that the case also to Gashonga coffee, the following table represents a certain strategies formulated in implementation of service delivery to their customer who need to be served day by day and for the right time.

Table 7: Strategies to enhance service delivery

Model	Beta	P value (sig)
The service delivery is attractive in our region	.114	.000
The firm give us different kind of motivation as to keep relationship with their customer and attract new ones	.226	.003
The firm receive our complaining immediately and verbally as the way of improving customer care	.443	.000
Provision of branches can improve service provided by our firm	.254	.004
Increasing the firm's equipment can help business to reach everywhere	.381	.000
The firm provide enough training to their works	.548	.000
My firm organize field work to visit their stakeholder in their firms	.285	.001

Source: Primary data, July 2022

Table 7, show that the results of The service delivery is attractive in our region $\beta=.114$, p value $=.000$; The firm give us different kind of motivation as to keep relationship with their customer and attract new ones $\beta=.226$, p value $.003$; The firm receive our complaining immediately and verbally as the way of improving customer care $\beta=.443$, p value $.000$; Provision of branches can improve service provided by our firm $\beta=.254$, p value $=.004$; Increasing the firm's equipment can help business to reach everywhere $\beta=.381$, p value 000 ; The firm provide enough training to their works $\beta=.548$, p value $.000$; My firm organize field work to visit their stakeholder in their firms $\beta=.285$, p value $=.001$; as the table show the strategies to enhance firm sustainability can

bust their working performance and make their firm to sustain in their operation and make their customer to stay therefore those strategies when it became implemented it can be the way of success.

4.4 Challenges to service delivery in the firm

Some challenges were asked in order to know some hindering or obstacles matters in this regards, that customer of this firm pass through sometime and the way move on even if they occur. By the use of Pearson Product moment correlation was computed in table below gives the summary of the correlation coefficient as well as the coefficient determination on challenges of service delivery on firm sustainability

Table 8: Challenges to service delivery in the firm

Correlation	R	R ²	P
I take a lot of time (distance) to reach on the firm headquarter	.336	0.112	.003
Sometimes business delay to pay the farms	.730	0.518	.000
The firm use different platforms that are easily accessible for every former who work with them	.251	.063	.029
Business has enough tools to reach everywhere	.361	.130	.001
I always communicate to firm when there is some difficulties and get response in right time	.313	.097	.006
It is not easy for illiterate to communicate with the firm	.568	.322	.000
The firm delay to respond on customers complaining	.491	.244	.000
Poor workers qualification hinder development of our firm	.537	.288	.000

Source: Primary data, July 2022

the table show us that there is a relationship between different items that are being compared in my study, where we have find that challenges that can be occurred in business and strategies that can be in measures as the way to improve the working conditions and as a cure of the challenges, there is relationship between distance to reach on the firm headquarter (**R**= .336, **P**= .003) The coefficient of determination (**R**²= .112) revealed that 11.2% , and Provision of branches can improve service provided by our firm. My firm organize field work to visit their stakeholder in their firms correlate with Business has enough tools to reach everywhere ranked on (**R**= .361, **P**= .001) the coefficient of determination (**R**²= .130) revealed that 13.0%. My firm provide enough training to their works (**R**= .537, **P**= .000), The coefficient of

determination ($R^2 = .288$) ranked by 28.8%. The firm receive our complaining immediately and verbally as the way of improving customer care, The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .244$) ranked by 24.4% ($R = .491$, $P = .000$). The service delivery is attractive in our region ($R = .313$, $P = .006$), The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .097$) ranked by 9.7%. The firm give us different kind of motivation as to keep relationship with their customer and attract new ones ($R = .251$, $P = .029$), The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .063$) ranked by 6.3%. This implies that different strategies that business provides to their business by the use of these strategies can handle those challenges to improve their working condition and make their service to be delivered successful.

4.2.1. Services appreciation

Manager show that according to service appreciation their customer reveal their level of appreciation against the services provided by factory this improves that customer has different attitudes to make their satisfaction and for their appreciation .

the participant show that business to sustain and attract different customer they work as best as they can to make their service delivery at the factory to be good and she also tell the researcher that most of their customer agree that the service there is excellent.

4.2.2. Complain channels

For measuring the way customers show their dissatisfaction, the customers were found to using different channels. Where she said that some of their customer complain verbally, other they contact the manager, and they also use letters to show their dissatisfaction all of this is different channel of complaining that business receive to clarify this the respondent tell us that after receiving this complaining through those channel what they do is to make direct response to their customer as way of maintaining their customer.

4.2.3 Customers and factory partnership

Researcher asks why they keep their partnership as the customers of the factory, and they provided the following information, most of farmers highlighted that partner is based on the fact that they belong to the zoning of that factory. Also, our customer confirmed that the service is attractive. And finally, some forms declared that their partnership with the factory

4.3. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study revealed that customers of Gashonga Coffee are aware of their rights. The factory office staff showed that their customers present their complaint whenever there is a problem. The predominant complaint is about the delay of payment since coffee farmers and merchants are paid monthly, the business satisfy (meet with) our expectation were low (Mean=2.27, SD= 1.18). My firm engage in delivering process were low (Mean=2.13, SD= .914). According to Prendeville, S., Bocken, N. (2017) the challenge of achieving a more sustainable society is a systems problem, where the economy, society, and environment are all interdependent. The primary shortcoming of existing techniques of measuring sustainability is the lack of a systems perspective. For Gashonga coffee The service delivery is attractive in our region ($R = .313$, $P = .006$), The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .097$) ranked by 9.7%. The firm give us different kind of motivation as to keep relationship with their customer and attract new ones ($R = .251$, $P = .029$), The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .063$) ranked by 6.3%.

John, P. et all, 2014, service delivery is the practice of measuring, disclosing, and being accountable for organizational performance while working towards the goal of sustainable development. Concerning to the service delivery and business sustainability, the factory officers focused that their business has survived up to the moment due to their service delivery quality. The facilities at my firm help me to increase my welfare $\beta = .521$, p value = .000; The seminars planed by firm help us to get open mind and become more creative and innovative in our operation $\beta = -.519$, p value .000

For strategies of service delivery towards sustainability, the factory officers said that people's life and environment are protected, the service delivery is attractive in our region $\beta = .114$, p value = .000;. There is serious growth opportunity in this sector, and companies are looking for varied skill sets to meet their needs around sustainability to follow in an effort to design and implement a successful sustainability strategy (Mariadoss, B. J., Tansuhaj, P. S., & Mouri, N 2011).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research entitled "Examining the nexus between service delivery on firm sustainability. Case study of Gashonga coffee, Period of 2019-2022" covered four specific objectives:

assessing the perceptions of customers towards service delivery, the contributions of service delivery on firm sustainability of SMEs, and investigating the challenges and strategies to enhance service delivery towards firm sustainability.

Concerning the level of service delivery by beneficiaries, it was found that whenever there is dissatisfaction with service delivery beneficiaries do not keep quiet. the business satisfy (meet with) our expectation were low (Mean=2.27, SD= 1.18). My firm engage in delivering process were low (Mean=2.13, SD= .914). Therefore, it is concluded that service beneficiaries are aware of their rights because whenever they are not satisfied with the service, they raise their concern and tell out their problems.

In regards to the contribution between service delivery and business sustainability, it can be concluded that service delivery has an effect on business sustainability. This is due to the fact that among both the factory workers and customers some respondents confirmed that their partnership is sustained by the service they are offered and The firm contribute to social activities to improve standard of living like umuganda and other programs $\beta=-.230$, p value 002;. To illustrate these respondents asserted that the service they are offered is attractive and the factory workers declared that they are retained by the good care and advantage they gain from their job Our firm increase employment opportunity in our local area $\beta=.388$, p value .000;.

As for challenges to good service delivery, the prevalent problem was found to the delay of payment of the factory customers (coffee farmers and sellers). Our respondent confirmed that there is delay of the payment of their product. From this challenge as the way to handle and work in good way they put in measure like visiting their stakeholder and increase branches and equipment this can help their customer as well.

Coffee drying factories should find all means to pay their customers on time and ensure satisfaction of their customer as their stakeholder.

Coffee drying factories should invest enough money so as to ensure that they can afford yield from coffee farmers and reach to them everywhere.

Improve level of communication, technology and material facilities to be used in production and delivering process.

Coffee drying factories should set their own strategies to increase the quality of service delivery that fits for the sustainability of their specific businesses and the welfare of their stakeholders. The study recommend NAEB to work with the Private Sector Federation (PSF) and SMEs in order to reinforce sustainable policies in service delivery, Provide subsidies to farmers so as to

improve their activities and yield produced, Train farmers and industries owner in order to make good corporation among them, Provide market for them either internally or externally market as the motivation and exploitation of their work, Attract investors who makes the development of this sector.

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